

Non-destructive dendrochronology: Analysis of the influence of conservation agents in the wood structure with laboratory-based and synchrotron X-ray micro-computed tomography

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Abstract

Non-destructive dendrochronology plays an important role in the dating of outstanding archaeological objects. A prerequisite for successful dating of an object based on X-ray computed tomography (CT) is the quality of the measurement data, which is mainly influenced by the conservation method. The aim of this research was to investigate to what

INTRODUCTION

Cultural objects made of wood are only preserved under extreme conditions where degradation mechanisms are suppressed (Singh et al. 2022). If waterlogged archaeological wooden finds come to light, they must be conserved or they will be irreversibly damaged. Among these finds are some scientifically outstanding objects, such as the first substantial wooden wheels (Burmeister 2016). With objects of such importance in particular, dating is of major scientific interest. Due to the vulnerability of the objects, the method has to be non-destructive. Here X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) is a suitable technique that can be used to examine a sample at various levels of spatial resolution (Withers et al. 2021). This dating method has been used and further developed for several years now (Van den Bulcke et al. 2014, Martinez-Garcia et al. 2021).

Conventionally, the annual ring widths are recorded under an optical microscope with a measuring device accurate up to 0.01 mm (Westphal and Heußner 2016). The tree ring analysis in the μ CT data requires a high resolution in order to detect even very narrow tree rings, whose width can range from 0.01 to several millimetres. In addition to high resolution, the contrast in the μ CT images is also crucial for the visibility of the tree rings. In order to obtain sufficiently good μ CT data, the type of wood and the diameter of the examined object must be considered in addition to the equipment used (Grabner et al. 2007, Bill et al. 2012, Stelzner and Million 2015, Křivánková et al. 2018, Mori et al. 2019, Stelzner et al. 2021).

Data analysis is very difficult with wet objects, since the water overlays the wood structure and no structural information can be evaluated. In these cases, techniques like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are necessary (Mori et al. 2019). For conserved objects, the challenge is that agents introduced during conservation can reduce contrast, which can lead to difficulties in μ CT data analysis (Bill et al. 2012, Wiesner et al. 2016, Stelzner et al., 2023b). However, this is not always the case, as demonstrated by three positive case studies (Keefer et al. 2006, Belz et al. 2008, Daly and Ebert 2021).

In this study, three common conservation methods were tested to determine the extent to which they enable or impair non-destructive dating using μ CT: alcohol-ether-resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) 2000 with freeze-drying. These methods were

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extent the methods alcohol-ether-resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) 2000 with freeze-drying influence the visibility of the annual rings. For this purpose, conserved samples of pine and oak wood, respectively, were measured by laboratory-based X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) and the contrast in the data was compared. In addition, the structure was measured by synchrotron μ CT. The investigations showed that the alcohol-ether-resin as well as the melamine formaldehyde conservation methods stabilise the cell wall. In contrast, PEG is deposited to a certain extent in the cell lumen, which reduces the contrast and thus renders measuring the tree-ring width more challenging.

selected as they achieved the best conservation results in previously conducted comparative studies on the available sample material (Stelzner et al. 2022 and 2023a). The influence of the conservation methods on the contrast in the μ CT data was examined on samples of oak and pine wood, which are important wood species in dendroarchaeology (Towner 2002, Haneca et al. 2009). In addition, the different influence of conservation agents was investigated on a microscopic level using μ CT with synchrotron radiation. This method has already been used to detect conservation agents (Bugani et al. 2009, Christensen 2013, Christensen et al. 2015, Braovac et al. 2022). Very high spatial resolutions are possible, although only small samples can be examined. For this reason, core samples were taken from the conserved archaeological oak and pine for these further investigations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The archaeological sample material

For this study, the reference collection at the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA) in Mainz, Germany, was used (Table 1). The softwood sample (Pinus), pine is from an undated water pipe from Stralsund, Germany. The hardwood sample (Quercus), oak derives from a wooden construction for a Roman salt extraction plant. Prior to conservation, the condition of the samples was measured (Jensen and Gregory 2006, Macchioni et al. 2012). Both samples had low-degraded inner regions and high-degraded areas in the outer regions. This type of degradation is defined by de Jong (1975) as grade 2. Before conservation, the material was cut into samples of the same size and each was treated with the different methods (see Table 1): alcohol-ether-resin, melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) and PEG 2000 with freeze-drying.¹

Methodology

The μ CT measurements on the conserved wood samples were performed on a laboratory system (Diondo d2) equipped with an X-ray source (X-RAY WorX XWT-225 TCHE+). The source was operated in high-power mode, with an accelerating voltage of 120 kV and an emission current of 167 μ A with a 1 mm aluminium filtration. The sample was then rotated 360° and X-ray images were acquired in each position in continuous rotation mode. A Varex 4343 DX-I X-ray detector was used to acquire the X-ray projections at a pixel size of 139 μ m. The sample size of the pine samples varied between 130 and 200 mm/ \varnothing 90–120 mm and for the oak samples between 120 mm/ \varnothing 160 mm, respectively. The μ CT system accepts samples up to a diameter of 520 mm and a height of 650 mm. However, it is important to note that the maximum resolution is limited by the sample diameter divided by 6,000 (pixels). The distance between the X-ray source and the sample was approximately 250 mm, and the total distance between the X-ray source and the detector was 860 mm. This resulted in a magnification between 3.4 and 5.4 and a nominal voxel size of 32–44 μ m, as the resolution achieved depends on the size of the samples and setup geometry (Stelzner and Million 2015). A total of 3000 projection images were acquired per measurement during the 360° sample rotation. Siemens Healthineers CERA reconstruction software was used to convert the resulting projections into

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Table 1. Overview of the samples

Sample no.	Database ¹ no.	Genus	Residual basic density [%]	Conservation method
Pi1-Air	V03-01	Pinus	52	Treatment: air-drying ² Impregnation solution: none
Pi1-AIEt	V03-17	Pinus	60	Alcohol-ether-resin ³ Treatment: exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection of 3 % Paraloid B-72 solution in acetone. Impregnation solution: 70.7% diethyl ether, 16.1% dammar resin, 6.4% rosin, 3.2% dienol D102, 3.2% castor oil, 0.4% PEG 400
Pi1-K800	V03-41	Pinus	60	Melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) ² Treatment: bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polycondensation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60°C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish. Impregnation solution: 25% Kauramin 800 solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol)
Pi1-PEG1	V03-35	Pinus	60	PEG and freeze-drying ⁴ Treatment: starting with 10% PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40% at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30°C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25% PEG 2000 solution in ethanol. Impregnation solution: PEG 2000, 10–40% solution with tap water
Oa2-Air	V16-15	Quercus	67	Treatment: air-drying ² Impregnation solution: none
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	Quercus	74	Alcohol-ether-resin ³ Treatment: exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection of 3% Paraloid B-72 solution in acetone. Impregnation solution: 70.7% diethyl ether, 16.1% dammar resin, 6.4% rosin, 3.2% dienol D102, 3.2% castor oil, 0.4% PEG 400
Oa2-K800	V16-25	Quercus	61	Melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) ² Treatment: bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polycondensation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60°C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish. Impregnation solution: 25% Kauramin 800 solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol)
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	Quercus	70	PEG and freeze-drying ⁴ Treatment: starting with 10% PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40% at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30°C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25% PEG 2000 solution in ethanol. Impregnation solution: PEG 2000, 10–40% solution with tap water

Note: The treatments were carried out at specialised institutions: ²Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum, Zürich, Switzerland; ³Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (formerly RGZM, Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum), Mainz, Germany; ⁴Nationalmuseet, Copenhagen, Denmark

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a 3D image stack of approximately $3,000 \times 3,000 \times 3,000$ voxels based on the filtered back-projection Feldkamp algorithm (Feldkamp et al. 1984).

To investigate to what degree the conservation agent in the wood structure affects the visibility of the annual rings in the μ CT data, the quality of the data was evaluated by calculating the contrast. While importing the data into the VGStudio MAX 3.4 software, they were calibrated: the values from the background (air) and the most absorbing part of the wood (e.g. the medullary ray) were set to specific grey values, with the maximum and minimum possible for 16-bit data sets being 65,535 and 0, respectively. Within this possible 65,535 grey value scale, the background (air) was set to 10,000 and the material (wood) to 50,000 when calibrating the measurements. The grey value profiles were taken in the radial direction, with the distances being the same for each test series. In addition, care was taken to ensure that the profiles were recorded without gaps or inclusions in the wood that could affect the results. The length of the profiles was 100 mm (see Figure 1). The values were then exported. The image contrast C was calculated by dividing the difference between the maximum (I_{\max}) and the minimum (I_{\min}) by the mean ($I_{\bar{x}}$) of the grey-level profiles (Peli 1990):

$$C = \frac{I_{\max} - I_{\min}}{I_{\bar{x}}}$$

Figure 1. Grey value profile from laboratory-based μ CT measurements on (a) a pine sample conserved with PEG 2000 and freeze-drying and (b) an oak sample conserved with melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800)

The mean of two profiles was calculated to get the mean contrast of one sample.

For synchrotron μ CT analyses, core samples were taken from the wood samples with an increment borer (\varnothing 5 mm). Then, the sample size was reduced to 2 mm in diameter. Propagation-based phase contrast synchrotron μ CT scans were performed at the imaging cluster of the KIT light source at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology using a parallel polychromatic X-ray beam produced by a 1.5 T bending magnet spectrally filtered by 0.7 mm of aluminium. A fast, indirect detector system was employed consisting of a 12 μ m-thick LSO:Tb scintillator (Cecilia et al. 2011) and a diffraction limited optical microscope (Optique Peter, Lentilly, France). This was coupled with a 12 bit pco.dimax S4 high speed camera with 2016 \times 2016 pixels using an optical magnification of 10 \times , resulting in an effective pixel size of 1.22 μ m and a field of view of approximately 2.4 mm \times 2.4 mm. Scans were performed by taking 3000 projections over a 180 $^\circ$ sample rotation at 70 frames per second and at a propagation distance of \sim 7 cm. A control system concert (Vogelgesang et al. 2016) was used for automated data acquisition and online reconstruction of tomographic slices to ensure the quality of the data. Online and final data processing, including phase retrieval (based on the transport of intensity equation; Paganin et al. 2002) and tomographic reconstruction, were performed using the UFO/tofu frameworks (Vogelgesang et al. 2012, Faragó et al. 2022). Image cross-sections of the wood structure were visualised on the VGStudio MAX 3.4 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contrast

The results of the laboratory-based μ CT measurements are displayed in Figure 2. The data show that the contrast in the untreated, air-dried sample is higher than in the treated samples. Alcohol-ether-resin performs best here, as it has the highest contrast and thus the least influence on the wood structure. The second highest contrast was achieved by the melamine formaldehyde resin (Kauramin 800) and the lowest by the high molecular weight PEG 2000 with subsequent freeze-drying.

Figure 2. The contrast in the laboratory-based μ CT measurements. The contrast in the conserved wood samples was averaged over two measuring distances as a function of the wood species

Overall, these results are independent of the wood species selected and show similar trends, namely that the contrast is higher for softwood samples than for hardwood samples. However, a clear difference can be seen between the samples conserved with PEG followed by freeze-drying, in which the contrast of the oak samples is higher than that of the pine samples when compared with the samples treated with all other conservation agents, in which the contrast in the pine samples is higher.

Microstructure

The influence of the wood anatomy on the examination was investigated under higher resolution (Figures 3, 4). In addition to severe deformation, the untreated, air-dried pine sample also exhibits an open structure (Figure 3a). The cell walls have shrunk considerably, contracted and are clearly evident in the synchrotron μ CT data. On the cross-sectional images of the alcohol-

Figure 3. Synchrotron μ CT cross-section of (a) the unconserved air-dried pine sample and the conserved pine samples treated with (b) alcohol-ether-resin, (c) melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) and (d) PEG 2000 with freeze-drying

Figure 4. Synchrotron μ CT cross-section of (a) the unconserved air-dried oak sample and the conserved oak samples treated with (b) alcohol-ether-resin, (c) melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) and (d) PEG 2000 with freeze-drying

ether-resin conserved sample, there is little effect of the conservation treatment compared to the untreated reference (Figure 3b). The secondary cell walls in the latewood shrank. In contrast, the cell wall structure of the sample conserved with the melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) treatment is very compact (Figure 3c). The resin appears primarily to stabilise the cell walls. In contrast, the lumen of the tracheids of the sample conserved with PEG are filled in both the early and late wood (Figure 3d). This reduces contrast, which is also visible in the CT section images.

Severe deformations and collapse are also seen in the oak samples. Air drying has condensed the structure, which makes it stand out well against the background (Figure 4a). The open and porous wood structure is also characteristic for the alcohol-ether-resin method (Figure 4b). The conservation agent is not visible. The oak sample conserved with the melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) displays a porous structure and most of the cell lumen does not appear to be filled (Figure 4c). However, it shows that the medullary ray and smaller lumen are filled. In comparison with the unconserved sample, it can be assumed that these deposits can be attributed to the conservation agent Kauramin 800. The oak sample conserved with PEG also shows deposits of PEG in the lumen of the tracheids (Figure 4d). However, the large-lumen vessels are not filled even in the late wood. This leads to an increase in contrast compared to the softwood sample.

CONCLUSION

Non-destructive dendrochronology based on μ CT data is a promising method that can be successfully applied to conserved archaeological wood. The underlying feature for achieving this is the visibility of the annual rings. However, the contrast in the μ CT data has a decisive influence on the visibility of the annual rings in the measurement data. The contrast is lowered due to the conservation material incorporated into the structure. A comprehensive comparative study has already been published (Stelzner et al. 2023b and c). In the synchrotron μ CT data, the condition of the cell walls and, in some cases, the deposition of the conservation agent could be visualised. The alcohol-ether-resin method affected the condition of the wood structure, but the conservation agent was not visible, resulting in a very high contrast. Conservation with melamine formaldehyde (Kauramin 800) deposited the conservation agent mainly in the cell wall, which then stood out well against the background, producing a high contrast. When conservation is carried out with PEG and freeze-drying, the tracheid cell lumen is partially filled with PEG. This reduces the contrast and makes it more difficult to distinguish between early and late wood. As seen in this study, the type of wood also plays a role, as the conservation agent is predominantly deposited in low-volume lumina, for example tracheids. If large vessels are present, as in oak, they are not completely filled and the contrast is less affected.

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Data availability: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cutaway/>

NOTES

¹ More information about the reference collection can be found here: <https://www.rgzm.de/kur> (accessed 1 October 2019).

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